

A Study to Assess the Prevalence of Selfitis Among Undergraduate I Year Students of Selected Arts and Commerce Colleges of Bhopal City, Madhya Pradesh

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ABSTRACT

Selfies are exploding social media all over the world. The number of self-portrait photos posted online has grown rapidly as a function of the simultaneous growth of social networking and smart phone use. It has triggered a number of risk taking and offensive public behaviour, pushing the boundaries of safety and decorum. Hence, the following study was undertaken to assess the prevalence of Selfitis in the upcoming generation of today's world, whose life mostly revolves around social media and friends. To assess the prevalence of Selfitis among undergraduate I year students. To associate the prevalence of Selfitis among undergraduate I year students with selected socio-demographic variables. Non-experimental univariate descriptive survey approach was used to determine the prevalence of Selfitis among undergraduate I year students of Arts and Commerce Colleges (n=200). Selection of the institution was done by non-probability convenient sampling technique and undergraduate I year students were selected by non-probability purposive sampling technique from Bhopal city, Madhya Pradesh.

The modified Selfitis Behaviour Scale developed by Janarthanan Balakrishnan and Mark D. Griffiths was used for data collection. The findings revealed that the overall prevalence of Selfitis was 97.5% (195) and 2.5% (5) of individuals did not have Selfitis and prevalence of acute Selfitis was higher i.e. 76.92% (150) and that of chronic Selfitis and borderline Selfitis was 11.28% (22) and 11.8% (23) respectively. The mean and standard percentage of the score was 49.3850 and 15.05357 respectively. The prevalence of Selfitis was higher in males (52.82%) as compared to females (47.18%). Hence, it is evident that there is significant prevalence of Selfitis among undergraduate I year students. Except gender none of the socio-demographic variables influenced the prevalence of Selfitis. The craze of selfies is turning out to be very harmful for adolescents because it is at this age that identity of an individual develops and if these unreal standards of appearance are bombarded on the young mind, it will have a catastrophic effect on the whole generation.

KEY WORDS: prevalence of selfitis, acute selfitis, borderline selfitis, chronic selfitis.

INTRODUCTION:

The word 'selfie' was including in the Oxford English Dictionary in 2013, and it was clear that this photo trend was here to stay for a long time of course, people have been painting—and photographing—self-portraits for centuries, but the quick immediacy of a selfie has become ubiquitous with today's lifestyle. No one comes to know when does a fun photo become an obsession? Defined as an “obsessive taking of selfies,” the concept of Selfitis first made the rounds online in 2014.

In 2014, stories appeared in national and international media claiming that the condition of “Selfitis” (the obsessive taking of selfies) was to be classified as a mental disorder by the American Psychiatric Association and that the condition could be borderline, acute or chronic.

The APA classified Selfitis during its annual board of directors meeting in Chicago. The disorder is called Selfitis and is defined as the obsessive-compulsive desire to take photos of oneself and post them on social media as a way to make up for the lack of self-esteem and to fill a gap in intimacy.

According to the APA, there are three levels of the disorder:

- **Borderline Selfitis:** It can be defined as taking photos of oneself at least three times a day but not posting them on social media.
- **Acute Selfitis:** In this a person takes photos of one's self at least three times,

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a day and posting each of the photos on social media.

- **Chronic Selfitis:** It is an uncontrollable urge to take photos of oneself round the clock and posting the photos on social media more than six times a day.

However, the stories were a hoax but this did not stop empirical research being carried out into the concept. Researchers at Nottingham Trent University in the UK and the Thiagarajar School of Management (TSM) in Tamil Nadu began investigating the phenomenon. They conducted interviews with a group of 225 Indian university students in an attempt to create what they called the Selfitis Behaviour Scale (SBS). They confirmed its existence and developed the 'Selfitis Behaviour Scale' which can be used to assess its severity. Participants were based in India because the country has the most users on Facebook, as well as the highest number of deaths due to attempts of taking selfies in dangerous locations.

The United States Department of Transportation estimated that during 2014, the so-called "year of the selfie", 33,000 people were injured while driving and using a cell-phone in some fashion, which can include talking, listening, and "manual button/control actuation" including taking, uploading, downloading, editing, or opening of selfies. A 2015 survey by Erie Insurance Group found that 4% of all drivers admitted to taking selfies while driving.

A Google search reveals that from 2014 to mid-2016, 75 people have died while attempting selfie in 52 incidents worldwide of which 54 have been recorded in India. The mean age of the victims was 23.3 and 82% of which were male. Fall from a height, drowning and rail accidents are the top three modes of death. Large-scale use of smart phones worldwide and underlying risk in selfie behaviour is the culprit.

PURPOSE OF THE STUDY:

According to a report in the Washington Post, the greatest number of selfie deaths in the world occurred in India. Of at least 27 "selfie-related" deaths around the world last year, about half occurred in India. This social media craze is now turning out to be extremely dangerous.

Selfitis - The new epidemic?

The first known selfie-related death occurred on 15 March 2014, when a man electrocuted himself on top of a train.

In January 2015, three students died while attempting to take a selfie close to a speeding train while they were on their way to Agra.

On 23rd March 2015, seven youths in Nagpur

drowned in a lake, while attempting to take a selfie. Their boat tipped over when all of them stood up to pose for the picture.

On January 10, 2016, three young girls were swept out into the Arabian Sea while taking selfies in Bandstand in Bandra. A man who jumped in to save them also died.

On February 1, 2017, 16-year-old Dinesh Kumar had gone to Chennai's Vandalur Zoological Park with his friends. But a fun day out turned fatal for Dinesh when he decided to take a selfie next to a speeding train.

In 2017, October, three youngsters from Bengaluru were crushed by a train while they took selfies.

In 2018, 13-year-old Tanzir fell to his death when he slipped off an over bridge in Jharkhand while taking a selfie with his friends on February 11.

A study conducted by Satish Saroshe et.al. in Indore (2016) among 100 students to assess for prevalence of selfie syndrome in young adults shows that around 11% people accepted that they take selfies daily, 3% said that they take selfies for attention, 31% said they have other reasons for taking selfies, self-objectification and narcissism. Overall 29% of people have done something crazy to look nice for a selfie, 16% of people had negative experiences.

Hence, the investigators felt the need to do a study on this topic as according to a report by Carnegie Mellon University and Indraprastha Institute of Information Technology, Delhi (IIIT Delhi) it was pointed out that India accounts for a startling 128 out of a total 213 selfie deaths recorded from 2014 to the present. Prevalence of Selfitis is increasingly high in the current scenario and the majority of individuals are unaware of this particular syndrome. We need to raise awareness because there are people who are struggling but do not know that their struggle is important or that what they are facing is a battle that is worth fighting.

MATERIALS & METHODS:

Since the study was aimed at assessing the prevalence of Selfitis among undergraduate I year students a non-experimental descriptive univariate survey approach was used. The study sample consisted of 200 undergraduate I year students of selected Arts and Commerce colleges of Bhopal city, Madhya Pradesh.

A structured questionnaire was used to obtain data on demographic variables. Data on prevalence of Selfitis was collected using modified Selfitis Behaviour Scale developed by Janarthanan Balakrishnan and Mark D. Griffiths in 2017.

The content validity of the tool was established by 15 experts from the field of Psychiatry, Psychology, Mental Health Nursing, Statistics and Sociology. Reliability was computed by split half method and was calculated to be $r = 0.79$ and thus the tool were highly reliable.

Pilot study was done on 20 samples to confirm the feasibility of conducting the main study. The data gathered was quantitative data. The responses were rated and tabulated in the form of frequencies and percentage. The data was analysed statistically using chi-square test.

MAJOR FINDINGS OF THE STUDY

Following are the major findings of the study:

SECTION I:

Socio-demographic variables:

Sixty four percentage of the undergraduate students were of 18 years. Majority (52.5%) were males whereas 47.5% were females. 99% were unmarried and 88% were Hindu's and 51.5% belonged to a nuclear family.

73.5% of fathers and 65.5% of mothers of undergraduate I year students were graduates and above. 44.5% of the fathers were self-employed and 35.5% were government employees. On the other hand, 76.5% of mothers were homemakers. The monthly income of 86% of the samples was 15,001 and above. 95.5% of undergraduate students lived in urban areas.

Majority i.e. 98.5% have access to smartphones and among them 56% have it for 3 years and above and 92% have a 4G network subscribed on their smartphones.

SECTION II:

Assessment of prevalence and severity of Selfitis among undergraduate I year students:

The overall prevalence of Selfitis was 97.5% and 2.5% of individuals did not have Selfitis and prevalence of acute Selfitis was higher i.e. 76.92% and that of chronic Selfitis and borderline Selfitis was 11.28% and 11.8% respectively. The mean and standard percentage of the score was 49.3850 and 15.05357 respectively.

Hence the hypothesis H_1 i.e. there will be significant prevalence of Selfitis among undergraduate I year students was accepted.

SECTION III:

Association between prevalence of Selfitis and selected socio-demographic variables age, gender,

religion, family income etc:

The association between prevalence of Selfitis among the samples with selected socio-demographic variables was statistically tested by applying chi-square test. From the table, it was evident that except gender none of the socio-demographic variables have significant association with prevalence of Selfitis. The prevalence of Selfitis was higher in males (52.82%) as compared to females (47.18%).

Hence the hypothesis H_2 i.e. there will be a significant association of Selfitis among undergraduate I year students with their selected socio-demographic variables at 0.05 level of significance was rejected.

CONCLUSION:

The following conclusions are drawn on the basis of the present study findings after data analysis:

- The overall prevalence of Selfitis was high i.e. 97.5% and prevalence of acute Selfitis was 76.92 % and that of chronic Selfitis and borderline Selfitis was 11.28 % and 11.8 % respectively.
- Except gender none of the socio-demographic variables have significant association with prevalence of Selfitis among undergraduate I year students. The prevalence of Selfitis was higher in males (52.82%) as compared to females (47.18%).

IMPLICATIONS:

The findings of the study on prevalence of Selfitis suggest several implications for nursing education, nursing administration, nursing research and community health nursing.

NURSING EDUCATION:

The education system must equip the nursing workforce to attend the needs of the diverse of the populations it serves. Psychiatric mental health registered nurses work with individuals, families, groups, and communities, assessing their mental health needs.

Thus, the implications for psychiatric-mental health nurses are broad and challenging.

Nurse educators need to add process addictions, such as Selfitis, to nursing curricula, and continuing education on the topic is also necessary. Nurses in all settings should use screening instruments to assess addiction when completing an interview.

Educational initiatives can also help to raise awareness on the negative effects of selfies.

NURSING PRACTICE:

1. Nurses must be able to identify the selfie addicts and refer them for early treatment.
2. Adolescents should be encouraged to spend more time outdoors in recreational activities to promote healthy development.
3. Nurses can help the patients in attending the individual therapy, cognitive behaviour therapy, dialectical behaviour therapy etc. They can conduct insight-oriented therapy.
4. Nurses must motivate the selfie addicts to form Selfie addict's anonymous groups to stay away from selfies.
5. The nurse serves as a community resource and will share information with community groups, treatment centres or self-help groups.
6. Behavioural counselling and cognitive behaviour emphasizing on self-motivation and self-control on unnecessary use of social media, giving quality time to family and friends.

NURSING ADMINISTRATION:

1. Nurses can organize individual counselling programs to improve their life skills, to inculcate good habits, to instil hope and to boost their self-esteem and also to have a balanced diet, adequate exercises, rest and relaxation.
2. Nurses can protect the public from selfie addiction through continuous education regarding dangerous zones, especially in the tourist spots to prevent selfie related injuries and deaths.
3. Efforts can also be made to identify a healthy way of using new media and introducing educational programs regarding responsible use of new media.
4. Educate teachers can then begin the moral education of children from an early age to help them realize that appearance is not everything as there are other aspects of personality such as intelligence, and good nature of a person, which would be used to judge a person.
5. Health education programs can be conducted to educate other professionals including teachers, guidance counsellors and administrations.

NURSING RESEARCH:

1. The need to expand education and incorporate new knowledge requires the scientific community to come together for this new generation addiction disorder and a lot of

research is required for the same before it affects a large population of the world.

2. Prospective large surveys are needed including a large number of persons who are actively involved on such social media to find out the underlying psycho-social factors responsible for selfie syndrome and the possible consequences of this syndrome.

RECOMMENDATIONS:

Based on the findings, the following recommendations are offered for future research:

1. A descriptive study to assess the effect of Selfitis on the self-esteem of adolescent children
2. A study to assess the relationship between mental health and level of Selfitis.
3. A study to assess the knowledge of nursing students regarding Selfitis.
4. A study to assess the impact of the number of likes on psychological well-being of students.
5. A comparative study to assess the level of Selfitis among females and males.
6. A co-relational study to assess narcissistic features, self-esteem and Selfitis among females.
7. A descriptive study to assess human and environmental factors which place individuals at greater risk of developing Selfitis.

LIMITATIONS:

1. The size of the sample studied was limited to 200 undergraduate I year students.
2. The study was confined to selected geographical area; hence generalization is not possible.

There is an old proverb that states, "A journey of a thousand miles begins with one step". It is time for physicians and health care workers to embark on the journey.

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Cite this article as: Thomas M & Shaji S: A Study to Assess the Prevalence of Selfitis Among Undergraduate. PJSR. 2022;15(1): 31-36.
Source of Support : Nil, Conflict of Interest: None declared.